

4 Benefits of Resistance Training

Cardiovascular Health

Resistance training helps prevent cardiovascular disease such as heart disease and type II diabetes

Increased Bone Density

Resistance training also increases bone density which reduces risk of developing Osteoporosis

Muscle Growth

Muscle growth can be achieved through strength training which can negate the effects of muscular atrophy later in life

Mood and Mental Health

Finally, resistance training can lead to overall improvements in mood and mental health

